

AUTHENTIC APPLICATION EXAMPLES IN MATH LECTURES THROUGH PEER TEACHING (CONCEPT)

Susanne Hilger¹
TH Köln
Köln, Germany

Angela Schmitz
TH Köln
Köln, Germany

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ABSTRACT

Engineering students often miss the connection between mathematics and the engineering disciplines. One solution to this problem is to integrate application examples into the math lectures. However, it is challenging for mathematicians to find adequate applications and to present them in an authentic manner.

We describe a concept of integrating application examples through peer teaching: A student who has already completed the mathematics course is involved in the preparation and presentation of such examples. As a result, the examples are very authentic since they are developed and presented by a person knowing the applications, the learners' motivation is high due to peer teaching, and the new

¹ *Corresponding Author*

Susanne Hilger

susanne.hilger@th-koeln.de

material is high-quality owing to the supervision by the lecturer. Surveys conducted for each application example reveal that the concept is well accepted.

The paper describes the steps in the development of application examples of different length and mathematical depth and gives recommendations on how to implement the concept successfully into math lectures.

1 INTRODUCTION

Mathematics courses are important for the education of engineers at universities [1], but the link to the engineering disciplines is sometimes missing [2] and the course is seen as a hurdle [3]. This can lead to low motivation and interest in mathematics among engineering students [4].

1.1 Bringing different academic levels together (peer teaching)

Students' motivation and learning effects can generally be strengthened by peer teaching [5]. Several benefits have been documented across the literature for both tutors and tutees. Tutors benefit in particular from the intensive active engagement with the subject matter and from explaining it [6]. An advantage for tutees is a similar cultural and linguistic reference and a more direct speech and confidence between tutor and tutees [7].

In the following we use the term "peer teaching" in the sense that we engage major students as partners in the development and presentation of teaching material. Such concepts are applied in [8] and [9], for example. Croft et al. [8] describe a project where major students are involved as co-creators of screencasts for first-year math lectures. Bovill et al. [9] gives an overview of approaches where students are involved as co-creators of teaching approaches, course design and curricula. Yet, these concepts encounters resistance from many lecturers as they fear that the quality of the resulting content may be insufficient [7].

1.2 Bringing different disciplines together (application examples)

There are various concepts to establish a closer connection between, amongst others, engineering and mathematics in engineering degree programmes [10]. One possibility is to integrate applications from the engineering disciplines into the mathematics courses. Such material should be as authentic as possible to create a link between mathematics and the engineering disciplines [4]. However, this idea includes the challenge for mathematicians to find appropriate applications [11] and to present them in an authentic manner [12].

1.3 Our concept

The concept presented in this paper combines both concepts, i.e. "Bringing different academic levels together" and "Bringing different disciplines together": The lecturer and an advanced student together develop application examples, and the student presents them in the lecture. This leads to high-quality and authentic application examples as well as to authentic presentations. With this project we hope to create a stronger connection between the mathematical and the application topics within the

given institutional and temporal conditions and in this way making the relevance of mathematics for the engineering programme more explicit.

1.4 Overview over the paper

The concept was conducted during a mathematics course for rescue engineers in the master's programme at a technical university in Germany. Students of this programme "obtain a specialized skill set allowing them to develop innovative and efficient concepts in hazard control and prevention as well as safety engineering" [13]. The mathematics course mainly includes topics in statistics and probability. It consists of a weekly lecture, in the form of seminar teaching using slides, and a weekly problem session.

In this paper we describe in detail all steps of the concept as it was carried out in that course in the winter term 2021 together with a major student (section 2). Then an accompanying evaluation of the intervention regarding the students' perspective on the application examples is described, and results are presented (section 3). Finally, the concept is discussed, and research perspectives and recommendations on how to implement the concept in other educational settings are given (section 4).

2 DESCRIPTION OF THE CONCEPT

In this section we explain in detail the steps that lead to the embedding of an example into the lecture. The steps are shown in Figure 1 and described afterwards. The fourth step sometimes made it necessary to return to the third step.

Fig. 1. Steps needed for the successful implementation of the concept

The project was realised with a (male) participant of the course of the previous semester who had achieved a very good grade and who had working experience in rescue engineering. We employed the student as an assistant for the project.

2.1 Suggestion (student)

Before the start of the semester, the student was assigned to search for applications of mathematics from the lectures of other engineering subjects, the related literature, and his work environment. He presented the results of his research to the lecturer.

2.2 Selection and embedding (lecturer)

The lecturer examined the collection of applications regarding the mathematical content and the fit with the lecture material. In the end, six examples were selected. We briefly describe two of the six examples, a short one and a long one, both receiving a very good evaluation by the students.

The example number 3 treated the mathematical topic of transformation of data (statistics). It consisted of a table with deployment data of twelve months for four fire stations, with a large accumulation of deployments in the month March (Figure 2).

The task was to decide which of the four stations was unusually busy in March. For a

meaningful comparison of the four stations the deployment data had to be transformed into standardised values. The student came up with the application himself based on his experience as a member of the volunteer fire brigade.

Fire station	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
1	7	11	31	12	12	10	10	9	9	11	13	14
2	23	34	56	43	36	35	27	26	24	32	43	41
3	2	3	5	3	4	3	4	3	2	6	4	4
4	3	5	12	6	3	1	3	4	4	5	2	6

Fig. 2. Number of deployments for four fire stations

In another example (number 5), the use of various discrete probability distributions such as Poisson distribution, binomial distribution, geometric distribution and uniform distribution was needed. Deployment data from a rescue service location was provided (Figure 3), and it had to be estimated how many rescue resources had to be kept on hand at what time in order to ensure a high level of operational safety for the missions. The idea for this application came from a standard book for rescue engineers [14].

Total number of missions in 2020	12400
Rescue vehicles provided	3
Average duration of a mission (unit)	58 minutes

Fig. 3. Deployment data from a rescue service location

2.3 Preparation (student)

The student prepared the selected examples for a presentation. He was provided with the slides for the lecture in which the example had to be embedded so that he could fit the example well into the context. Furthermore, he was asked to build on the mathematical knowledge that had already been covered and to use matching notations. In addition, we explained to him in advance how to prepare an example in a good educational way. We used the modelling cycle according to Blum and Leiss [15] as a basis (Figure 4).

Fig. 4. Modelling cycle for the preparation of application examples ([15], modified)

The example number 3 was initially prepared by the student in a spreadsheet programme (Excel). The sheet included the number of deployments for four fire stations in twelve months (Figure 2) and the calculations for standardising the data. After quality assurance by the lecturer (see the next step), the student additionally prepared slides showing in detail the steps in the modelling cycle (Figure 4).

The example number 5 was also initially prepared exclusively in Excel. The student's approach first was very similar to the presentation in the literature [14]. He didn't show the simplifications and assumptions made for the setting of the model (steps from "Real situation" to "Mathematical model" in Figure 4) or which probability distributions were used ("Using mathematics" in Figure 4). In several cycles (see Figure 1 and see the next step), a number of slides were created that addressed the different steps in the modelling cycle (Figure 4).

2.4 Quality assurance (lecturer)

The student presented his material to the lecturer. The lecturer critically examined the preparation and the presentation, especially with regard to the setting and use of the mathematical model, the mathematical solution in the model, the fit to the course material and the quality of the presentation. In-depth questions by the lecturer on the application context improved the understanding of both and as a consequence also the student's presentation (see step 5). This discussion partly required the student to revise the preparation of the material (back to step 3).

The example number 3 required very little time on the part of the lecturer. The student supplemented his initial presentation via Excel sheet with teaching slides and he added a quiz to activate the students.

Example 5 was more elaborate in its preparation, on the part of the student as well as on the lecturer. All the modelling necessary for the mathematical solution was worked out very carefully. Hidden assumptions made in the applications were explicitly described and discussed and provided with a suitable discrete probability distribution. Several times, we returned to step 3.

2.5 Presentation and discussion (student)

The student explained and presented the examples in the lecture, sometimes with integrated quizzes or independent work phases in smaller groups, and he led the subsequent discussion. Questions concerning the application context could be answered directly by him, the 'expert' for the application. The lecturer was also available for questions (of a more mathematical nature) and for clarifications. The presentation of example 3 lasted about 10 minutes, whereas the presentation of example 5 filled a big part of the session (45 minutes).

3 EVALUATION OF THE CONCEPT

Our subjective impression was that the examples were very authentic and well received by the students who participated in the course. Nevertheless, we also wanted to systematically evaluate the examples in order to learn more about the acceptance of the concept, to better understand the students' perspective, and to

obtain ideas for improvement from the students' perspective. In this section we explain the methodological tool of the evaluation and present the results.

3.1 The evaluation instrument

To measure the students' evaluation of the examples, the students answered a survey questionnaire after the presentation of each example. The examples should be evaluated regarding the criteria "motivational", "applicability" and "authenticity" which were developed in [4] and which we adapted to the setting of the examples. Respondents were given options using a six-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 6 (strongly agree) to measure their agreement on the statements of the questionnaire. Five items build the scale "motivational", one being for example "The reference to an application has aroused my interest." The scale "applicability" consisted of three items, one being for example "This example has improved my ability to work on tasks with an engineering context." The criterion "authenticity" is checked with one item, namely "The application reference is authentic: a real engineering problem is solved with the help of mathematics." (All sample items were translated by the authors.)

In addition, we had the following statement rated, on the same scale: "I liked that the example was presented by a student."

3.2 The sample

The study involved 7 to 18 students who were enrolled in the master's programme of rescue engineering. The six examples that were integrated into the lecture were evaluated by a different number of students: The first one was rated by $n=18$ students, the second by $n=17$, the third by $n=11$, the fourth by $n=12$, the fifth by $n=7$, and the last by $n=10$.

3.3 The results of the evaluation

Fig. 5. Mean values of the three evaluation criteria in the six examples

Descriptive analysis for the evaluation criteria (Figure 5) reveals that all examples were evaluated as being very authentic (mean values ranging from 4.39 to 5.00), the one with the highest mean value is example 5. The examples 1 to 5 seem to be quite

motivating (mean values between 3.90 and 4.12) and applicable (mean values between 3.93 and 4.58). In the example 6 the criteria “motivational” and “applicability” are rated weaker than in the other examples (3.10 and 3.47).

The mean scores for the examples in the item “I liked that the example was presented by a student” are 4.56, 4.88, 4.55, 4.33, 5.29, and 4.40, so they are consistently well above average (3.50).

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

We summarize the concept and describe success factors and challenges, discuss the evaluation of the project and give recommendations on how to implement the concept in other courses.

4.1 The concept: summary, success factors and challenges

The concept successfully combines the ideas of “Bringing different academic levels together” and “Bringing different disciplines together” as explained in section 1, and additionally solves the disadvantages associated with the two approaches, namely the concern for the correctness of a student presentation [7] and the missing authenticity of the presentation by a mathematician [12].

Different levels are brought together by the collaboration with an advanced student during the development of the material and the presentation of the examples. The didactic and professional quality of the presentation is ensured by the interplay between student and lecturer (in particular step 4, the quality assurance).

This close cooperation also brings together different disciplines: an engineering student and the mathematics lecturer. The involvement of advanced students with an engineering background makes the examples more convincing. The authenticity is reinforced by the fact that the student himself/herself presents the application and is directly available for discussions, especially on the context of the application. This is an important difference to the concept in [8], where screencast videos are developed together with students and then integrated into the course as video material.

The concept is a small intervention that can be easily accommodated within the given institutional framework and requires little time. The cooperation with the student is needed as the mathematician lacks the knowledge of the application context. Remark that short as well as long examples were successfully embedded into the course. A side effect of the project is the learning effect that the tutor has concerning the mathematics and the educational tools – the student’s presentations improved from example to example, and the student also confirmed an increase in understanding in an interview that concluded the project.

Central for a successful implementation of the concept was the collaboration with a student who was enrolled in the same study programme, had a good understanding of mathematics and who had experience in an engineering work environment, thus knowing the work place of engineers quite well.

Other important factors were the close cooperation between the lecturer and the student, the demand for a deep understanding of both the application and the mathematical content (on the part of both the student and the lecturer), the use of the modelling cycle in the preparation of the material and the attention to matching notations and a good fit with the lecture material.

A challenge even before the start of the project was to find a student with the mathematical and engineering background willing to develop teaching material and to present it. During the collaboration, it was challenging to develop mutual understanding, in particular to match the lecturer's 'mathematics language' and the student's 'engineering language'.

4.2 The evaluation: Summary, limitations and research perspectives

The results of the survey show that the examples were perceived by the students as very authentic and that they very much appreciated that a student had presented them. The example number 5 that took the most time to prepare, had the most mathematical input and took the longest to be presented was judged the most authentic. In addition, most of the examples were received as very motivating and applicable. Only the sixth examples was rated worse in these two criteria. A reason for this could be that the mathematical topic used in this example (hypothesis testing) is quite difficult for students.

Limitations of the evaluation result from the small size of the sample. Either the concept should be tested and evaluated in courses with a larger audience in order to gain better quantitative insight into the students' evaluation of the examples and the role of the student giving the presentation, or, with a similarly small sample as here, interviews should be conducted in order to obtain qualitative results.

In addition to a better methodological implementation of the study, it would be interesting to investigate if there is a difference in the evaluation of the examples when they are not presented by a student, whether the concept changes the students' motivation in the long term as a result of the intervention, and which value the tutor found in the intervention.

4.3 Recommendations

The concept can be transferred both to beginners' math lectures and to any other subject where connections between different disciplines can be created. The new material can be used beyond the specific implementation in one semester with a particular student, as the quality is good and the lecturer understands the application well after the implementation.

A challenging step is to find a student from a higher semester, ideally with work experience and good grades in the subject. We recommend asking students who have previously taken the subject.

REFERENCES

- [1] Alpers, B., (2013), A Framework for Mathematics Curricula in Engineering Education. A Report of the Mathematics Working Group. In B. Alpers, M. Demlova, C.-H. Fant, T. Gustafsson, D. Lawson, L. Mustoe, B. Olsson-Lehtonen, C. Robinson, D. Velichova (Eds.), *European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI)*.
- [2] Tang, K.-S., and Williams, P. J., (2018), STEM literacy or literacies? Examining the empirical basis of these constructs, *Review of Education*, Vol. 7, No. 3, pp. 675-697.
- [3] Harris, D., Black, L., Hernandez-Martinez, P., Pepin, B., and Williams, J. (2015). Mathematics and its value for engineering students: what are the implications for teaching? *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, Vol. 46, No. 3, pp. 321-336.
- [4] Wolf, P., (2017), Anwendungsorientierte Aufgaben für Mathematikveranstaltungen der Ingenieurstudiengänge [Application-oriented tasks for mathematics courses in engineering degree programmes], Springer Spektrum, Wiesbaden.
- [5] Hattie, J. A. C., (2009), Visible learning. A synthesis of over 800 meta-analyses relating to achievement, Routledge.
- [6] Topping, K. J., (2005), Trends in Peer Learning, *An International Journal of Experimental Educational Psychology*, Vol. 25, No. 6, pp. 631-645.
- [7] Flores, M., and Duran, D., (2013), Effects of Peer Tutoring on Reading Self-Concept, *International Journal of Educational Psychology*, Vol. 2, No. 3, pp. 297-324.
- [8] Croft, T., Duah, F., and Loch, B., (2013), 'I'm worried about correctness': undergraduate students as producers of screencasts of mathematical explanations for their peers – lecturer and student perceptions, *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, Vol. 44, No. 7, pp. 1045-1055.
- [9] Bovill, C., Cook-Sather, A., and Felten, P., (2011), Students as co-creators of teaching approaches, course design and curricula: implications for academic developers, *International Journal for Academic Development*, Vol 16, No. 2, pp. 133-145.
- [10] Froyd, J. E., and Ohland, M. W., (2005), Integrated Engineering Curricula, *Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 94, No. 1, pp. 147-164.
- [11] Hallström, J., and Schönborn, K. J., (2019), Models and modelling for authentic STEM education. Reinforcing the argument, *International Journal of STEM Education*, Vol 6, No. 22.
- [12] Pennell, S., Avitabile, P., and White, J. R., (2005), An interdisciplinary, multise semester project relating differential equations and engineering, Proceedings of the 2005 American Society for Engineering Education Annual Conference & Exposition.
- [13] https://www.th-koeln.de/en/academics/rescue-engineering-masters-program_7780.php
- [14] Lindemann, T., (2021), Feuerwehrbedarfsplanung [Fire brigade requirements planning], Kohlhammer.

- [15] Blum, W., and Leiß, D., (2007), How do students and teachers deal with modelling problems? *Mathematical Modelling*, Woodhead Publishing, pp. 222-231.